

**POETICS OF SOCIAL CHRONOTOPE IN "REBELLION AND
OBEDIENCE" BY ULUGBEK HAMDAM AND "THE MOON AND
SIXPENCE" BY SOMERSET MOEM**

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ANNOTATION

In this thesis, the scientific research consists of studying the concepts of man and society in Uzbek and English literature, that is, in the works of Ulugbek Hamdam and Somerset Maugham, their comparative analysis and finding their uniqueness will be briefly covered. The scientific novelty of the research conducted on these works is that the similar and different aspects of the concept of interaction between man and society in Uzbek and English literature were carried out on the basis of a comparative analysis. In the works of writers, the specific characteristics of the ideas of "man and society", the causes and consequences of the problems in mutual relations, the influence of these complications on the human psyche, and the role of this work in the analysis of the artistic light have been studied.

Key words: *human, society, character, reality, socio-psychological concepts, system, analysis, research.*

It is clear to all of us that literature is the art of words, the expression of the people's heart, the herald of truth and justice. Due to our national independence, a number of updates are taking place in our literature, as in all fields. In addition to formal and substantive updates in the works of literary critics and artists, unique new views are also manifested in the views of the art of speech and creativity. "The literature of the period of independence is turning from the literature of problems, from the literature that raises actual issues, to the literature that artistically explores and examines the layers of the human psyche."

In the work of Ulugbek Hamdam and Somerset Maugham, the issue of man and society is covered in one or another aspect in our literature, but it has not been studied as a whole. The relevance of the scientific work is determined by the scientific-artistic

approach to the issue of macro- and micro-chronotope, comparing only one example of the writers' creativity. The relevance of this scientific work is determined by this.

The relevance of the study is as follows:

- a) the need to deeply research the role of the concept of man and society in Uzbek and world literature and controversial theories;
- b) formation of relations between man and society and research of this idea;
- c) analysis of artistic interpretation as one of the elements determining the principles of forming relationships in the works of writers;
- d) consists of analyzing the artistic image of social factors that created

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Little by little white snow will fall.

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Isn't the meaning of being born and living in the world to feel this beauty, to pay attention to it?" Akbar used to reflect on the stork flying in front of his eyes and instantly melting away. enjoying the snow..."

...Finally, love! Only now he is trying to teach me something, and I am also excited with my breath catching in my throat. The secret of the matter, I still do not know it better, but the greatest wisdom of life is held as in love. Rub and let it be, rub and don't be deceived. I can't bear it if my expectations turn out to be a mirage again. Despite the guilt, I will kill myself. However, he has already lost his sweetness..." The role of artistic psychologism in creating a microchronotop of an artistic hero cannot be denied, and each of its available methods increases the full understanding and effectiveness of the work. Also, the events are described by the inner experiences of the hero, his feelings, thoughts and judgments, and the dynamics of his thoughts. In this, one feeling gives rise to another feeling, one thought gives rise to another thought, they complement each other and change their quality. This form makes it possible to show sharp turns in the fate and thinking of the characters, which is why some researchers call it the form of "dialectic of the soul".

Akbar opened his eyelids, moved slowly and followed the large notebook lying open on the writing table and wrote: "A heart without rebellion will not obey." He added

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“Rebellion” next to the word “Obedience” written in letters. Akbar had been looking for this name for several years, but he didn't find it!... – “REBELLION and OBEDIENCE”, here it is - a very difficult way to become a human being, this is the fate written on the forehead of mankind...

In the novel “The Moon and Sixpence” through the dynamic principle, the psyche of the hero is expressed through his actions, facial expressions and gestures, his behavior in various life situations and his words, in essence, it is similar to the way of revealing the psyche of the characters of the dramatic work. therefore, the dynamic principle is sometimes described as the “dramaturgical method” of psychological analysis. “I tell you I’ve got to paint. I can’t help myself. When a man falls into the water it doesn’t matter how he swims, well or badly: he’s got to get out or else he’ll drown.”¹

“I paused, and I looked at him searchingly.

“What’s the good of trying to humbug me?” I said.

“I don’t know what you mean.”

I smiled.

“Let me tell you. I imagine that for months the matter never comes into your head, and you’re able to persuade yourself that you’ve finished with it for good and all. You rejoice in your freedom, and you feel that at last you can call your soul your own. You seem to walk with your head among the stars. And then, all of a sudden you can’t stand it anymore, and you notice that all the time your feet have been walking in the mud. And you want to roll yourself in it. And you find some woman coarse and low and vulgar, some beastly creature in whom all the horror

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With these tools, the writer can reflect the circumstances of the hero’s life in his picture. Therefore, it is not a mistake to think that the creation of a microchronotope of an image through artistic psychologism can come from the author's goal and style. Artistic psychologism generally interprets issues such as the essence of fiction, the general laws of literary development, its role and tasks in the life of society, the nature

¹ Somerset M. The great novels and short stories of Somerset Maugham. Skyhorse and Skyhorse Publishing. 2014 – p. 191.

² Somerset M. The great novels and short stories of Somerset Maugham. Skyhorse and Skyhorse Publishing. 2014 – p. 216.

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of a work of art and its structure, and reveals general laws on this basis. With its help,

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